

Preparation of Azamerocyanines and Evaluation of the Effect of Introduction of Nitrogen Atom in the Chromophoric Chain

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Verification of Forster's and Knott's rule has been achieved with the help of absorption data of a number of azamerocyanines derived from various heterocyclic compounds. With the help of the same data the relative order of acidities of ketomethylene compounds has also been evaluated. The effect of substituents on absorption has also been studied.

The present work describes the preparation of some azamerocyanines derived from various 2-amino heterocyclic nuclei and ketomethylene compounds. Their absorption spectra have been studied and utilised in the evaluation of the effect of the replacement of $=\text{CH}-\text{CH}=\text{}$ by $=\text{N}-\text{CH}=\text{}$ in the chromophoric chain. The relative order of acidities of ketomethylene compounds have also been evaluated. The effect of substituents on the absorption of these dyes have also been studied.

For the preparation of the dyes the following 2-amino heterocyclic nuclei were used : (i) Benzothiazole, (ii) 4-phenyl thiazole, (iii) 4,5-diphenyl thiazole, (iv) alpha- and beta-naphthathiazole. 2-Amino-4-phenyl thiazole and 4,5-diphenyl thiazole were prepared by condensing the acetophenone and desoxy benzoin respectively with thiourea in the presence of iodine¹. Alpha- and beta-Naphthathiazoles were prepared by cyclising the corresponding aryl thioureas with bromine in the presence of chloroform². The thiazoles were quaternised by heating with methyl iodide in a sealed tube.

The following ketomethylene compound whose intermediates were used for the preparation of these dyes were prepared by standard methods : (i) Rhodanine, (ii) pyrazolone, (iii) thiobarbituric acid, (iv) phenyl oxazolone and substituted oxazolones, (v) thiothiazolone.

The azamerocyanines were prepared by condensing the quaternary salts of 2-amino heterocyclic compounds with the intermediates of ketomethylene compounds in alcohol and triethylamine.

In the dyes of the above type, the excited structures carrying $-\overset{-}{\text{C}}-$ have greater significance than the structures carrying $-\overset{+}{\text{C}}-$, because structures carrying $-\overset{-}{\text{C}}-$ contain one double bond more than the structures carrying $-\overset{+}{\text{C}}-$. When $=\text{CH}-$ is replaced by $=\text{N}-$, the relative contribution of (Ib : X = N) to the resonance hybrid will be more than (Ib : X = CH) because of greater stability of $-\overset{-}{\text{N}}-$ as compared to $-\overset{-}{\text{CH}}-$. According to Forster's rule³, the increasing tendency of the methin chain to retain the characteristic charge would result in the decrease in absorption maximum. Hence the replacement of $=\text{CH}-$ by

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1. L. C. King and R. J. Halvacek, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 3722.
2. P. N. Bhargava and B. T. Haliga, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **35**, 807.
3. F. F. Forster, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1932, **45**, 548.

= N - in (I) would result in a hypsochromic shift. This has actually been realised by measuring the absorption maxima data (Table I) of various azamerocyanines derived from different nuclei.

TABLE I

Absorption maxima of merocyanines and their aza analogues derived from variable acidic and basic nuclei

Nature of the nucleus 'A'	Nature of the nucleus 'B'	Absorption maxima in $m\mu$		Expected shift	Observed shift	
		X=CH	X=N			
Benzothiazole	Pyrazolone	490	400	Hypsochromic	90	
	Rhodanine	510	424		-do-	86
	Thiobarbituric acid	500	415		-do-	85
	Oxazolone	520	440		-do-	80
	Thiothiazole	530	500		-do-	30
4-Phenyl thiazole	Pyrazolone	500	400	-do-	100	
	Thiobarbituric acid	500	405	-do-	95	
	Oxazolone	530	440	-do-	90	
	Thiothiazole	520	500	-do-	20	
4,5-Diphenyl thiazole	Pyrazolone	522	410	-do-	112	
	Rhodanine	550	450	-do-	100	
	Oxazolone	560	465	-do-	95	
	Thiothiazolone	545	500	-do-	45	
alpha-Naphththiazole	Rhodanine	543	440	-do-	103	
	Thiobarbituric acid	515	420	-do-	95	
	Oxazolone	540	450	-do-	90	
	Thiothiazole	549	500	-do-	49	
beta-Naphththiazole	Pyrazolone	514	435	-do-	79	
	Rhodanine	542	440	-do-	102	
	Thiobarbituric acid	515	425	-do-	90	
	Oxazolone	540	450	-do-	90	
	Thiothiazolone	550	500	-do-	50	

By the application of Forster's rule to the absorption data of the above compounds, another interesting aspect i.e., the determination of relative acidity of ketomethylene nuclei used has been studied. Considerations stated below led us to explore the possibility of this novel approach for determination of relative acidities.

The hypsochromic shift resulting from the replacement of $X = CH$ by $X = N$ in (I) is primarily caused by the resulting increased significance of the excited structure Ib. Significance of the latter structure to the resonance hybrid depends on the extent of charge separation. As the acidity of the nucleus 'B' is increased (i.e., it possesses increasingly greater electron attracting property); the contribution of the excited structure (Ib) to the resonance hybrid is diminished proportionately and further as the acidity of the nucleus 'B' is gradually reduced the contribution of the excited structure becomes increasingly significant. Since \bar{N} is more stable than \bar{C} , the replacement of $=CH-$ by $=N-$ would result in increasing hypsochromic shift with decreasing electron attracting property of the nucleus. It follows, therefore, that if the basic nucleus is kept constant, the hypsochromic shift will be less for a merocyanine derived from a strongly acidic and more for a merocyanine derived from a weakly acidic one. In the present investigation the acidic nuclei used are oxazolone, thiothiazolone, rhodanine, thiobarbituric acid and pyrazolone. It may be seen from Table I that hypsochromic shift observed on replacement of $=CH-$ by $=N-$, for the acidic nuclei, thiothiazolone, oxazolone, thiobarbituric acid, rhodanine and pyrazolone with benzothiazole as the basic nucleus are 30, 80, 85, 86 and 90 $m\mu$ respectively. Similar orders of hypsochromic shifts were also seen in case of 4-phenyl thiazole, 4,5-diphenyl thiazole and α - and β -naphthathiazoles. The decreasing order of acidity will be thiothiazolone > oxazolone > thiobarbituric acid > pyrazolone > rhodanine which is in excellent agreement with our previous findings⁴.

Knott's rule⁵ on the other hand, is rather empirical and states that if the carbon atom, at which replacement takes place is separated from the active auxochromic atoms by an odd number of conjugated atoms, a hypsochromic shift results, whilst a separation by an even number of atoms results in a bathochromic shifts.

EXPERIMENTAL

5-(3-Methyl-4-phenyl thiazoline-2-ylidene amino methylene)-3-phenyl rhodanine: 5-Ethoxy-methylene-3-phenyl rhodanine (0.20 g.) and 2-amino-4-phenyl thiazole methiodide (0.32 g.) were refluxed in absolute ethanol and triethylamine (2 drops) for ten minutes. It was cooled and the solid which separated was crystallised from ethanol. Yield—83%. M.P. 215°. (Found: C, 58.42%; H, 3.50%. $C_{20}H_{15}N_3S_3O$ requires C, 58.67; H, 3.66%).

The analytical data, m.p. etc., of the related azamerocyanines derived from different ketomethylene compounds are given in the Table II.

5-(3-Methyl benzothiazoline-2-ylidene amino methylene)-3-phenyl rhodanine: 5-Ethoxy methylene-3-phenyl rhodanine (0.19 g) and 2-amino benzothiazole methiodide (0.29 g.) were refluxed in absolute ethanol and triethylamine (few drops) for five minutes. After cooling

4. K. K. Satpathy, A. Nayak and M. K. Rout, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 799.
5. E. B. Knott, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 1024.

the solid separated and was crystallised from ethanol. Yield—65%. M.P. 250°. (Found : C, 53.30; H, 3.20%. $C_{18}H_{13}N_3S_3O$ requires C, 53.99; H, 3.57%).

TABLE II

Azamerocyanines derived from 2-amino-4-phenyl thiazole

Nature of the nucleus 'A'	Yield %	M.P. °C	λ_{max} in $m\mu$	% Carbon		% Hydrogen	
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
Pyrazolone	75	169	400	67.21	67.38	4.83	4.80
Thiobarbituric acid	70	250	405	65.15	65.32	4.10	4.03
2-Phenyl oxazolone	68	218	440	69.49	69.60	4.27	4.35
2- <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl oxazolone	65	168(d)	452	63.12	63.24	3.57	3.69
2- <i>p</i> -Tolyl oxazolone	65	215	438	70.00	70.19	4.70	4.73
2- <i>p</i> -Anisyl oxazolone	65	220(d)	435	67.11	67.20	4.47	4.53
Thiothiazolone	50	175(d)	500	59.48	59.57	3.91	4.02

(d) denotes decomposition.

The analytical data and m.p. etc., of the related azamerocyanines derived from variable acidic nuclei are given in the Table III.

TABLE III

Azamerocyanines derived from 2-amino benzothiazole

Nature of the nucleus 'A'	Yield %	M.P. °C	λ_{max} in $m\mu$	% Carbon		% Hydrogen	
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
Pyrazolone	60	193	400	65.40	65.52	4.43	4.59
Thiobarbituric acid	75	250	415	63.77	63.83	3.73	3.83
2-Phenyl oxazolone	65	220	440	64.39	64.47	3.87	3.88
2- <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl oxazolone	70	240	450	55.40	55.48	3.09	3.22
2- <i>p</i> -Tolyl oxazolone	65	250	438	65.25	65.33	4.30	4.29
2- <i>p</i> -Anisyl oxazolone	55	180(d)	435	59.64	59.63	3.88	3.95
Thiothiazolone	59	150	500	57.36	57.43	3.70	3.78

5-(3-Methyl-4,5-diphenyl thiazoline-2-ylidene amino methylene)-3-phenyl rhodanine : 5-Ethoxy methylene-3-phenyl rhodanine (0.19 g) and 2-amino-4,5-diphenyl thiazole methiodide (0.39 g.) were refluxed in absolute alcohol and triethylamine (few drops) and the product was isolated as before. Yield—57%. M.P. 245. (Found : C, 64.30; H, 4.01%. $C_{26}H_{19}N_3S_3O$ requires C, 64.33; H, 3.92%).

The analytical data, m.p. etc., of the related azamerocyanines prepared by the above procedure from different ketomethylene compounds are given in the Table IV.

TABLE IV

Azamerocyanines derived from 2-amino-4,5-diphenyl thiazole

Nature of the nucleus 'A'	Yield %	M.P. °C	λ_{\max} in $m\mu$	% Carbon		% Hydrogen	
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
Pyrazolone	45	95	410	72.03	72.00	5.03	5.11
2-Phenyl oxazolone	56	206	465	74.29	74.34	4.45	4.51
2- <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl oxazolone	55	220	470	68.41	68.49	4.60	4.61
2- <i>p</i> -Tolyl oxazolone	60	245	460	74.43	74.51	4.87	4.85
2- <i>p</i> -Anisyl oxazolone	60	250	455	71.82	71.84	4.58	4.65
Thiothiazolone	40	145	500	64.85	64.93	4.16	4.20

5-(3-Methyl beta-naphthathiazoline-2-ylidene amino methylene)-3-phenyl rhodanine : 5-Ethoxy methylene-3-phenyl rhodanine (0.19 g) and 2-amino beta-naphthathiazole methiodide (0.34 g.) were refluxed in the appropriate medium and the product was isolated as above. Yield—63%. M.P. 218°. (Found : C, 60.92; H, 3.43%. $C_{22}H_{15}S_3N_3O$ requires, C, 60.97; H, 3.46%).

The analytical data, m.p. etc., of the different azamerocyanines derived from beta- and alpha-naphthathiazoles with various ketomethylene compounds are recorded in the Table.V and VI respectively.

TABLE V

Azamerocyanines derived from 2-amino beta-naphthathiazole

Nature of the nucleus 'A'	Yield %	M.P. °C	λ_{\max} in $m\mu$	% Carbon		% Hydrogen	
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
Pyrazolone	50	250	435	69.11	69.17	4.71	4.76
2-Phenyl oxazolone	65	250	450	72.26	72.33	4.08	4.11
Thiobarbituric acid	50	250	420	69.87	66.92	3.82	3.85
2- <i>p</i> -Chloro phenyl oxazolone	70	250	475	62.86	62.93	3.51	3.57
2- <i>p</i> -Tolyl oxazolone	70	250	435	69.18	69.17	3.99	4.01
2- <i>p</i> -Anisyl oxazolone	60	250	430	66.45	66.50	4.02	4.09
Thiothiazolone	50	248	500	61.69	61.74	3.85	3.89

TABLE VI

Azamerocyanines derived from 2-amino alpha-naphththiazole

Nature of the nucleus 'A'	Yield %	M.P. °C	λ_{max} in $m\mu$	% Carbon		% Hydrogen	
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
Rhodanine	63	218(d)	445	60.91	60.97	3.41	3.46
Pyrazolone	57	187(d)	435	69.14	69.17	4.72	4.76
Thiobarbituric acid	59	250	430	66.87	66.92	3.81	3.85
2-Phenyl oxazolone	67	250	450	72.29	72.33	4.08	4.11
2- <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl oxazolone	77	250	470	62.86	62.93	3.52	3.57
2- <i>p</i> -Tolyl oxazolone	70	250	440	69.11	69.17	3.98	4.01
2- <i>p</i> -Anisyl oxazolone	60	250	438	66.43	66.50	4.08	4.09
Thiothiazole	40	170	500	61.70	61.74	3.87	3.89

(d) denotes decomposition.

The authors are grateful to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi for providing a research fellowship to one of them (A.N.).

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Received February 3, 1970